

NURTURING YOUNG MINDS: THE VITAL ROLE OF COMMUNITY LEARNING CENTER IN IMPLEMENTING THE CURRICULUM AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS ON EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT IN ZAMBOANGA CITY

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Nurturing Young Minds: The Vital Role of Community Learning Center in Implementing the Curriculum and its Effectiveness on Early Childhood Development in Zamboanga City

Ethel P. Binarao,* Maricor E. Gegone, Riaza A. Sahaji

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examined the role of community learning centers in Zamboanga City in fostering early childhood development through effective curriculum implementation. Early childhood education plays a critical role in shaping the developmental outcomes of young children, particularly in cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor domains. Guided by Systems Theory, it investigates the relationship between teacher qualifications, training, and developmental outcomes in cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor domains. A descriptive-correlational design was used, with 30 Day Care teachers from four barangays—Tugbungan, Lunzuran, Talon-Talon, and Santa Catalina—participating in a structured survey. Findings show that most teachers hold a bachelor's degree and have extensive teaching experience, but training frequency varies. Activities promoting problem-solving, early literacy, numeracy, and physical skills are consistently implemented, supporting children's development. However, weak correlations were found between teacher qualifications and perceived curriculum effectiveness. The study emphasizes the need for regular teacher training and resource allocation to improve curriculum delivery. It also recommends periodic curriculum reviews to address evolving educational needs. By addressing these areas, community learning centers can enhance their impact on early childhood education, providing equitable opportunities for children's holistic development. The findings offer practical insights for educators, policymakers, and administrators to strengthen early learning systems and improve developmental outcomes.

Keywords: *community learning centers, early childhood development, curriculum implementation, teacher training*

Introduction

Learning begins in infancy, long before formal education starts, and continues throughout life. Early learning paves the way for future success, with early achievements fostering later accomplishments, while early failures often lead to persistent challenges. Success or failure during this foundational stage profoundly influences a child's educational journey and subsequent lifelong learning. Melhuish et al., (2015) highlights that early childhood years are pivotal, as interventions during this stage have long-lasting effects on learning and motivation. As a society, we cannot afford to delay early childhood development until adulthood or even school age, as interventions at that point may be less effective.

Day care centers are critical in this endeavor, offering young children a nurturing environment that promotes cognitive, social-emotional, and physical growth. They also serve as community hubs, providing family support, outreach, and social services. Effective early childhood interventions can help reduce inequalities and build peaceful, prosperous societies. Studies emphasize that quality pre-primary education is the foundation of lifelong learning, and its success determines the effectiveness of subsequent educational stages. Day care centers play a pivotal role in supporting the cognitive, social-emotional, and physical development of young children, while also fostering community engagement and socialization.

As a cornerstone of early childhood education, day care centers provide a safe, nurturing environment where children can grow, learn, and thrive. Beyond their immediate impact on children's lives, day care centers also serve as hubs for family support, community outreach, and social services. Gervacio (2015) found that preschool children attending daycare exhibit significant improvements in cognitive competencies, with many transitioning from "Competent" to "Very Competent" levels after structured educational interventions. Furthermore, a study compared the developmental progress of kindergarten pupils with and without daycare exposure, revealing that pupils with daycare experience performed significantly better in the seven developmental domains essential for transitioning to kindergarten. Notably, unexposed pupils struggled in self-help and expressive language skills, underscoring the critical role of daycare education in early childhood development (Futalan et al., 2023).

Day care centers play a pivotal role in early childhood care and development (ECCD) by providing a nurturing environment where young children can begin building essential cognitive, emotional, and social skills. These centers are critical in addressing the developmental needs of children under five years old, a period highlighted by the Early Years Act of 2013 (RA 10410) as vital for holistic growth. Despite their importance, challenges persist, such as inequitable distribution and variable program quality across regions. Many municipalities, particularly low-income ones, lack sufficient day care facilities, limiting access for vulnerable populations. Strengthening day care centers through improved infrastructure, access to quality resources, and trained caregivers can significantly contribute to preparing children for formal education while addressing broader developmental goals (Ulep et al., 2023).

Childhood is a critical period for the development of physical, intellectual, social, and emotional skills. These skills are malleable and can be developed through both formal and informal learning experiences. As the government implements the program education for all in providing day care centers program it must not overlook the importance of ensuring comprehensive support for ECCDW's who

directly contributes to better learning outcomes for children in sustaining foundational and developmental skills in literacy and numeracy proficiency are most likely to increasing parallel of learning outcome, it is high time ECCDW's takes a crucial part towards holistic and effective learning developmental center in society. Therefore, this study aims to Identify qualifications of Early Childhood Developmental Worker and its training backgrounds in teaching community learning centers in Zamboanga City. To know its developmental domains practices in learning centers base from the curriculum in order to meet the standards required in terms of Cognitive Skills, Fine Motor Skills and Gross Motor Skills and know its significant relationship between the Early Childhood Community Development Worker qualifications in teaching day care and its effectiveness in implementing the curriculum. By gathering information from day care schools in Zamboanga City specifically from Barangays Tugbungan, Lunzuran, Talon-Talon, and Santa Catalina, this study will help address the issues and provide comprehensive early childhood education and care, including day care centers and provides learning opportunities access to resources, workshops, and training for educators.

Research Questions

This study aims to evaluate the role of community learning centers in Zamboanga City in implementing the curriculum and its effectiveness in fostering early childhood development across the cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor domains. Specifically, the study aimed to identify the following:

1. What are the qualifications and training backgrounds of teachers in community learning centers in Zamboanga City in terms of:
 - 1.1. education; and
 - 1.2. training?
2. What activities do community learning centers implement to develop:
 - 2.1. cognitive skills;
 - 2.2. fine motor skills; and
 - 2.3. gross motor skills?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the qualifications of day care teachers and the effectiveness of kindergarten curriculum implementation?

Literature Review

Role of Community Learning Centers in Early Childhood Development

Day care centers are pivotal in promoting young children's development, well-being, and readiness for formal education. Globally, high-quality childcare has been shown to significantly impact children's long-term learning, health, and social development. Community-based childcare centers, such as those in Malawi, address critical early childhood developmental needs through nutrition, cognitive stimulation, and community support, while also helping reduce poverty and illiteracy (Munthali et al., 2014). Similarly, Sharma (2015) highlighted the importance of community learning centers in fostering holistic child development by integrating social and educational programs. Locally, the Philippine government's Early Child Development (ECD) Project (1999) and the institutionalization of the Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) Act (2002) have focused on improving child welfare by establishing governance structures, delivering targeted services, and addressing the needs of disadvantaged children. These initiatives underscore the importance of accessible day care centers in providing early learning opportunities.

Teacher Qualifications and Training in Community Learning Centers

The qualifications and training of teachers play a vital role in the effectiveness of community learning centers. Globally, the professional development of educators is emphasized as key to improving curriculum implementation and ensuring high-quality learning experiences (Anderson et al., 2003). Gyekye-Ampofo et al. (2023) highlighted that well-trained educators contribute significantly to the developmental outcomes of young learners. Locally, studies have shown that teacher preparedness directly impacts children's readiness for school and developmental progress. For instance, evaluations of Philippine community-based programs funded by the Department of Social Welfare revealed that well-trained service providers improved children's skills across various developmental domains (Behrman et al., 2005). These findings underscore the necessity of investing in teacher training to enhance curriculum delivery and child outcomes.

Developmental Domains in Early Childhood Education

Community learning centers focus on developing key domains essential for early childhood education, including cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skills. Cognitive development encompasses mental processes such as attention, memory, and problem-solving, which lay the foundation for future academic success. Magbanua (2023) emphasized the importance of fostering these abilities through structured and exploratory activities.

Motor skills, defined as the ability of the nervous system to control motion, are crucial in early childhood development and are divided into gross and fine motor skills. Gross motor skills involve large muscle movements, such as locomotor (e.g., walking, running), object control, and balance skills (Bardid et al., 2016). Fundamental motor skills, including stability, object control, and locomotor

movements, are essential for later participation in sports and other physical activities (Rudd et al., 2015). Fine motor skills, on the other hand, require precise coordination between the eyes, hands, arms, and limbs, allowing for movements such as picking up objects, threading, drawing, and dressing (Kokštejn et al., 2017; Johnston & Halocha, 2017). These manipulative skills, regulated by small muscles, develop slightly later than gross motor skills and necessitate patience and practice (Payne & Isaacs, 2017).

Motor development, as noted by Madrona (2014), aims to achieve control over the body to exploit its potential in interacting with the surrounding environment. This development impacts physical and mental health as well as cognitive achievement, especially in children with neurodevelopmental disorders (Hill & Khanem, 2009). Fundamental elements of motor skills, such as strength, durability, speed, agility, balance, and coordination, are vital not only for physical activity but also for overall development (Wang et al., 2004; Senturk et al., 2015). These elements involve the coordinated interaction of nerves, muscles, and bones, which collectively support locomotor (movement from one place to another), non-locomotor (stationary movements), and manipulative motor skills (movement involving objects).

By addressing these developmental domains, day care centers align their practices with curriculum standards, ensuring young learners develop the foundational skills necessary for successful transitions to formal education and beyond.

Curriculum Implementation and Effectiveness

Effective curriculum implementation is a cornerstone of early childhood education, ensuring that developmental milestones are met. Globally, well-structured curriculum models, such as those discussed by Sharma (2015) and Munthali et al. (2014), emphasize the alignment of learning goals with children's developmental needs. Locally, Philippine ECCD programs have demonstrated significant improvements in cognitive, physical, and social-emotional skills among children who have access to community learning centers. For instance, programs implemented in low-income barangays have successfully supported early formative education, showcasing the importance of targeted curriculum strategies in achieving positive child development outcomes.

Policies and Programs Addressing Early Childhood Education

Foreign and local studies underscore the critical role of policies and programs in improving the effectiveness of early childhood education through community development initiatives. Globally, comprehensive early childhood development programs have been shown to address disparities in school readiness, particularly for children from economically disadvantaged backgrounds. Anderson et al. (2014) highlighted that publicly funded, center-based programs help prevent developmental delays by reducing grade retention and special education placements. Additionally, the Education for All Global Monitoring Report (UNESCO, 2006) emphasized the long-term benefits of Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), including improved school readiness, child development, and economic returns. High-quality ECCE programs integrate educational activities, health care, and nutrition, with well-trained educators ensuring curriculum effectiveness in developing children's skills. Community-Based Early Childhood Care and Education (CBECCE) initiatives, such as those highlighted by Jacob and Falade (2022), demonstrate the importance of inclusive strategies to boost enrollment and reduce disparities, particularly in hard-to-reach areas.

Locally, the Philippine Early Childhood Development (ECD) project has strengthened national, regional, and local capacities to provide integrated and sustainable developmental services. These efforts have led to the institutionalization of policies and systems aimed at bridging gaps in child survival, development, and education, particularly in poor local government units (ADB, 2006). By expanding access to quality ECD services, these programs promote children's rights to survival and development while supporting parents in their caregiving roles.

Both foreign and local evidence highlights the importance of ensuring high-quality ECCE programs with well-trained educators and integrated services. Policymakers are urged to invest in capacity-building initiatives for teachers, prioritize access to high-quality ECCE programs, and address systemic gaps to ensure equitable opportunities for all children. These measures can have long-lasting benefits in reducing illiteracy and poverty while fostering holistic development for children across diverse communities.

The SEA-PLM (2019) National Report of the Philippines revealed that Grade 5 students who participated in Early Childhood Education (ECE) programs performed better in reading, writing, and mathematics compared to their peers who did not attend such programs. Moreover, ECE attendance has demonstrated benefits in children's school readiness, timely entry into primary school, and smooth grade progression. Parents of children with ECE experience reported that their children were capable of performing more language and mathematical tasks prior to primary school. These findings suggest that investing in ECE can significantly enhance children's learning outcomes in later years while mitigating disparities between advantaged and disadvantaged groups. To maximize these benefits, effective curriculum implementation is essential, supported by proper educator training, infrastructure development, and local government assistance in facilities and operations.

In the Philippine context, Community Learning Centers (CLCs) play a crucial role in implementing the curriculum within the Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) framework. While these centers are recognized for their potential to deliver quality early education, further research is needed to evaluate their actual effectiveness. Specifically, studies should assess how well CLCs contribute to the holistic development of children, particularly those from vulnerable backgrounds, by addressing cognitive, social, emotional, and physical domains. Additionally, empirical evidence is required to determine the success of CLCs in achieving key ECCD outcomes,

such as improved child health, school readiness, and early cognitive milestones. Understanding these aspects will help policymakers and stakeholders optimize the role of CLCs in enhancing the overall efficiency and equity of the education system.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilizes a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between teacher qualifications, training backgrounds, and the effectiveness of curriculum implementation in community learning centers. According to Salkind (2010), a descriptive-correlational design allows for the assessment of variables without manipulation, making it suitable for examining how teacher demographics, qualifications, and training practices relate to developmental outcomes in cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skills.

Respondents

The study involves 30 Day Care teachers selected from a total population of 40 across four barangays in Zamboanga City: Tugbungan, Lunzuran, Talon-Talon, and Santa Catalina. Respondents were chosen through random sampling to ensure representation across different socio-economic and geographic contexts. To be included in the study, teachers must have experience in implementing the early childhood education curriculum.

Instrument

Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire, divided into three sections: teacher qualifications and training backgrounds, incorporation of developmental domains into teaching practices, and perceptions of curriculum effectiveness. Responses were measured using a Likert scale to ensure comprehensive data collection. This was a researcher-made questionnaire, which underwent content validation by experts in early childhood education to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives.

Procedure

Researchers sought permission from relevant authorities and conducted data collection through scheduled visits to the community learning centers. Teachers were briefed about the study’s purpose, and the survey questionnaires were administered during these visits. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analyses to identify patterns and relationships.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participants were provided with an informed consent form detailing the study’s objectives, voluntary participation, and confidentiality assurances. All responses were anonymized, securely stored, and used solely for research purposes. Ethical clearance was obtained from the university’s research ethics committee prior to data collection.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the findings of the study on the role of community learning centers in Zamboanga City, focusing on the implementation of the kindergarten curriculum, teacher qualifications, targeted developmental domains, and their impact on early childhood development.

Problem 1: What are the qualifications and training backgrounds of teachers in community learning centers in Zamboanga City in terms of education and training?

Table 1. Educational Attainment, Major Field of Study, Years of Experience, and Training Frequency of Teachers

Variable	Categories	Frequency (N=30)	Percentage
Educational Attainment	High School Diploma	3	10%
	Associate's Degree	2	6.7%
	Bachelor's Degree	22	73.3%
	Master's Degree	2	6.7%
	Doctorate	0	0%
Major Field of Study	Early Childhood Education	9	30%
	Elementary Education	10	33.3%
	Special Education	2	6.7%
	Others	9	30%
Years of Experience	Less than 1 year	0	0%
	1–3 years	5	16.7%
	3–5 years	0	0%
	More than 5 years	25	83.3%
Training Frequency	Monthly	8	26.7%

Quarterly	9	30%
Annually	6	20%
Rarely	7	23.3%

The 30 teachers in community learning centers in Zamboanga City have diverse qualifications and training backgrounds. Most (73.3%) hold a bachelor's degree, with smaller percentages holding a master's degree (6.7%), an associate's degree (6.7%), or a high school diploma (10%). The majority specialize in education-related fields, including Elementary Education (10), Early Childhood Education (9), and Special Education (2), while 9 teachers studied other fields. Most teachers (25) have over five years of experience, with 5 having 1-3 years. Professional development participation varies, with 9 attending quarterly, 8 monthly, and 6 annually; 7 rarely engage in training. These findings highlight experienced teachers with varying qualifications and training frequency, indicating a need for more consistent professional development.

Problem 2: What are the developmental domains in the community learning centers practice base from the curriculum in order to meet the standards required for day care centers in terms of cognitive skills, fine motor skills, and gross motor skills?

The study examined the developmental domains addressed in the curriculum of community learning centers, focusing on cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skill development. Table 2 summarizes the frequency of activities aimed at these developmental areas.

Table 2. Frequency and Mean Score of Activities Supporting Cognitive, Fine Motor, and Gross Motor Skill Development (n=30)

Domain	Activity	Always (%)	Often (%)	Sometimes (%)	Rarely (%)	Never (%)	Mean
Cognitive Development	Problem-solving (e.g., puzzles)	53.3	33.3	13.3	0	0	4.4
	Early literacy (e.g., storytelling)	83.3	16.7	0	0	0	4.83
	Early numeracy (e.g., counting)	80	16.7	3.3	0	0	4.77
Fine Motor Skills Development	Writing or drawing	80	20	0	0	0	4.8
Gross Motor Skills Development	Small manipulatives (e.g., blocks)	60	20	20	0	0	4.4
	Outdoor play	60	30	10	0	0	4.5
	Structured physical activities	73.3	20	6.7	0	0	4.67

Table 2 presents the frequency of activities supporting cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skill development in community learning centers. Cognitive skill development activities, such as problem-solving puzzles, were "always" implemented by 53.3% of respondents, with a mean score of 4.4, indicating frequent use. Early literacy activities, including storytelling and letter recognition, were consistently applied, with 83.3% of respondents reporting "always" implementing them, resulting in the highest mean score of 4.83. Similarly, early numeracy activities like counting and sorting were "always" conducted by 80% of respondents, yielding a mean of 4.77. For fine motor skills development, writing or drawing activities were "always" used by 80% of respondents, with a mean score of 4.8, while small manipulatives, such as blocks, were "always" utilized by 60%, leading to a mean of 4.4. In terms of gross motor skills, outdoor play activities were "always" implemented by 60% of respondents, with a mean score of 4.5. Structured physical activities, such as obstacle courses, were "always" included by 73.3% of respondents, achieving a mean of 4.67. These results highlight a strong emphasis on early literacy (4.83) and numeracy (4.77) activities, as well as structured physical activities (4.67), demonstrating a well-rounded approach to supporting cognitive, fine, and gross motor skill development in community learning centers..

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the qualifications of day care teachers and the effectiveness of kindergarten curriculum implementation?

To address the third research question, the study analyzed the perceived effectiveness of the curriculum in developing cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skills, and its relationship with teacher qualifications. Pearson's correlations were computed to assess the relationships between educational attainment, experience, training frequency, and curriculum effectiveness. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix for Educational Variables and Developmental Domains

Variable	Cognitive Mean (r)	Fine Motor Mean (r)	Gross Motor Mean (r)
Educational Attainment	0.168	0.123	0.123
Years of Experience	0.170	0.027	0.027
Training Frequency	0.107	0.031	0.031

Note: Pearson's r values represent the strength and direction of the relationship between variables

A weak positive correlation was found between educational attainment and the developmental domains, but none were statistically significant (Cognitive Mean: $r = 0.168$, $p = 0.375$; Fine Motor Mean: $r = 0.123$, $p = 0.517$; Gross Motor Mean: $r = 0.123$, $p = 0.517$). Similarly, years of experience showed weak correlations with the developmental domains, but these were also not statistically significant (Cognitive Mean: $r = 0.170$, $p = 0.369$; Fine Motor Mean: $r = 0.027$, $p = 0.885$; Gross Motor Mean: $r = 0.027$, $p = 0.885$). The training frequency likewise showed weak correlations that were not statistically significant (Cognitive Mean: $r = 0.107$, $p = 0.575$; Fine Motor Mean: $r = 0.031$, $p = 0.870$; Gross Motor Mean: $r = 0.031$, $p = 0.870$).

However, the perceived effectiveness of cognitive development was moderately correlated with both fine motor ($r = 0.511$, $p = 0.004$) and gross motor ($r = 0.511$, $p = 0.004$) development, suggesting that as respondents perceived cognitive activities to be effective, they also rated fine and gross motor activities more positively. Moreover, a perfect positive correlation ($r = 1.000$, $p < 0.001$) was found between fine motor and gross motor development, indicating that those who rated fine motor activities highly also rated gross motor activities highly.

Overall, although there were no statistically significant correlations between educational attainment, years of experience, or training frequency with the perceived effectiveness of the curriculum, there were moderate correlations between cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor development, particularly in terms of cognitive activities influencing motor skill development.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Most teachers in Zamboanga City's community learning centers possess at least a bachelor's degree, with many specializing in Early Childhood Education. Their experience is generally extensive, but the frequency of professional training varies.

The curriculum effectively supports cognitive, fine motor, and gross motor skills, with teachers showing positive perceptions of its impact. However, qualifications alone do not strongly correlate with curriculum effectiveness, suggesting that teaching practices and resources play a more significant role.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

School leaders are encouraged to inspire teachers by providing more frequent and structured training on integrating developmental domains and modern teaching strategies to enhance curriculum implementation.

Teachers are encouraged to continuously innovate and expand their approach to include activities that support emotional and social development, alongside cognitive and motor skills.

Community Learning Centers are encouraged to foster collaboration between teachers and educational specialists to ensure access to necessary resources, guidance, and support for better curriculum delivery.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ethel P. Binarao

Saint Joseph School Foundation Incorporated – Philippines

Maricor E. Gegone

Tugbungan Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines

Riaza A. Sahaji

Sta. Barbara Central School

Department of Education – Philippines